

Column-stores conquering the geo-spatial domain.

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Earth observation sciences, astronomy, and seismology have large data sets which have inherently rich spatial and geo-spatial features. In combination with large collections of semantically rich objects which have a large number of properties, they form a new source of knowledge for urban planning, smart cities and natural resource management.

Modeling and storing these properties indicating the relationships between them is best handled in a relational database. A class of DBMSs, called column-stores, have proven efficiency for analytic applications on extremely large data sets. Column-stores have become the de-facto standard for managing large data warehouses. Although they have a proven track record in business analytics, will they obtain the same for Geo-spatial analytics?

Our research has the aim to create a spatial DBMS which loads data from different sources and converts it into a common format to enable 3D operations and analyses, such as 3D intersections, and semantic properties management.